

WEB-BON: THE DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT OF A WEB-BASED BARANGAY INFORMATION AND RECORD MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

Cris Norman P. Olipas, Ruth G. Luciano, Alexander S. Cochanco, Brenan Mei A. Delos Santos, Alecxis Elgin B. Cajucum, Fayshen L. Tabelin, Jerhome H. Taberna

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to design and develop a web-based Barangay Information and Record Management System. It integrated Short Message Service (SMS) to provide a more accessible means to distribute barangay announcements. The project utilized a developmental method of research. The proponents have designed and developed the system based on user requirements and specifications, observation and interview results among the key barangay officials, and analysis of the manual processes available documents.

The designed and developed web-based system has been developed using different software development analysis and design tools and models such as Gantt chart, Use-case Models, Entity-relationship models, and Data flow diagrams. The proponents were able to design and develop the system, and it was found out that the developed system could provide better means of delivering services at the barangay level.

INTRODUCTION

Barangay plays a significant role in the overall development of a municipality, a province, or a country. Barangay is an administrative unit in the Philippines consisting of 50 to 100 families (Merriam-Webster, n.d). Thus it is imperative to come up with development projects that would benefit the members of the

community. Today's technological advancement calls for a more innovative and progressive approach to handling different processes and activities at the barangay level. The integration of different technological innovations and products has been proven beneficial and advantageous in managing communities. Several projects in the past have shown that an Information and Record Management System can provide a significant positive impact, such as the studies of Pulumbarit and Suarez (2017), and Aparici and Ruelan (2018)

Typically, managing information and records at the barangay level can pose challenging tasks and activities such as difficulties accessing records, storing these records, and retrieving files and other vital barangay records. Imus, Magleo, Soriano, Mand (2018) have found out that recurring problems and challenges related to files and records can be solved by developing a Barangay Management Information Systems (BMIS). In the past, Javellana, Cainong, and Galvez (2015) have also cited that using barangay information and record management system could provide significant changes by adopting electronic services to optimize the performance in the barangay concerning records management. Further, Lado et al. (2017) assert that electronic files can be easily accessed, retrieved, and transmit; therefore, implementing an information system has proven to be effective and efficient.

Though several studies have been developed in the past, the proponents of this study designed and developed a web-based barangay information and record management system to contextualize a specific community's needs in the province of Nueva Ecija. The developed system provided a new approach to managing the barangay files and records using Web System Technology.

The purpose of this project was to enhance the quality of service in the barangay. It provided features on record keeping, retrieving, and view of files and records. Also, searching and accessing files and records were made easier and accessible. The system helped to process and visualized data and get information efficiently. It provided a database of barangay residents' information and included short message service support to announce important events in the barangay.

The project was also designed to provide solutions to the difficulties occurring in the barangay about records management. Through this project, the proponents aimed to provide better options for the barangay to manage their files and records properly, effectively, and efficiently.

Project Objectives

Generally, the proponents aimed to design and develop a Web-Based Barangay Information and Record Management System with Short Message Service (SMS).

Specifically, it sought to achieve the following goals and objectives:

To develop a module used for faster, more convenient, and more efficient means to search, insert, delete, and update barangay residents' information;

To construct a module that handles transactions such as events announcement and residents' notification for committed violations;

To provide a module that enables the residents to update their personal information easily;

To develop a module that quickly generates real-time reports;

To design a user-friendly system environment that allows the users to effectively, conveniently, and comfortably interact with the system.

Scope and Delimitations

This study was conducted in Barangay Santor, Bongabon, Nueva Ecija; thus, the processes considered and incorporated in the developed system conform to the barangay's needs. The study covered the design and development of the system. However, the implementation and assessment phase can be considered in the next stage of the study.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a developmental research method in which the proponents developed the system based on different data gathering tools and techniques such as interviews, observation, documentary analysis, and article review.

Data Gathering Tools and Techniques

In the interview, the proponents had time to talk to barangay key officials such as the barangay chairman and the barangay secretary. Figure 1 and 2 shows the conduct of the interview held in the barangay.

Figure 1: Interview with the Barangay Chairman

Figure 2: Interview with the Barangay Secretary

After interviewing to gather the necessary information for the system's design and development, the proponents were given a chance to observe and look at the different documents used in the barangay, such as the logbook for filing violations and the pile of residents' records and information. Through this, the proponents were able to draw necessary insights relevant to the development of the system. Figures 3 and 4 show the mode of recording and storing files and records using the manual process.

Figure 3: Log Book for Residents Violations

Figure 4: Pile of Residents' Barangay Records

Gantt Chart

To properly execute the system's design and development, the proponents constructed a Gantt chart that served as a guide in developing the project. Figure 5 shows the Gantt chart used in this study.

ID	Activities	August 2019				September 2019				October 2019				November 2019			
		W1	W2	W3	W4	W1	W2	W3	W4	W1	W2	W3	W4	W1	W2	W3	W4
1	Planning Stage																
2	Analysis																
3	Design - Back-End Design																
4	Design - Front End Design																
5	Testing																

Figure 5: Gantt chart of activities

Data Flow Diagram

A data flow diagram (DFD) was used to guide the proponents to understand the system's flow properly. It was essential to utilize DFD to illustrate how the system processed data and how entities interact with different processes and data storage included in the system. Figure 6 shows the level 0 diagram of the DFD of the system.

In the figure below, three major entities can be observed: barangay chairman, secretary, and residents. These entities have vital roles in the developed system. The data they produced were processed in the system through different modules as part of the overall web-based system.

Figure 6: Data Flow Diagram

In constructing the DFD, the proponents found out that having a comprehensive DFD would benefit the project's actual development. A detailed DFD, along with a detailed and comprehensive Use-Case diagram, would make the design and development of a system more comfortable and faster.

Use-Case Diagram

As the name implies, the Use-Case diagram was vital in designing and developing the web-based system to understand user interaction in the developed system. The use-case diagram shows the relationship between the user and the processes covered by the system. The diagram aided the proponents to understand further the user assigned roles and privileges in the developed system. Figure 7 presents the user-case diagram for the developed system.

Figure 7: Use-Case Diagram of the System

Normalization

Microsoft (2019) explains that data normalization is the process in which redundancy and inconsistency are eliminated by setting rules and establishing policies to protect both the data and the database itself. It utilizes tables and rows to organize the data to produce valuable results. The proponents of this study have constructed the database conforming to the rules of database normalization. Figure 8 presents the database normalization of the developed system on its third level state.

	tbl_announcement		tbl_barangay		tbl_blotter_records
PK	announcement_id		PK,FK	brgy_id	PK
	Description			brgy_name	Description
	case_date			Username	case_date
				Password	
				Logo	
	tbl_case		tbl_groups		tbl_officials
PK,FK	case_number		PK	group_id	PK
	Description			group_name	official_id
				date_added	official_name
					official_img
					official_Position
					insert_date
	tbl_caseload		tbl_punishment		tbl_residents
PK,FK	case_number		PK	punishment_id	PK,FK
	Description			punishment_name	brgy_id
					resident_id
					firstname
					lastname
					nickname
					birthday
					place_of_birth
					sex
					contact_number
					province
					municipality
	tbl_purok		tbl_violation		
PK	purok_name		PK	violation_id	
	add_time			violation_name	

Figure 8: Database Normalization

Entity-Relation Diagram

Like Use-case models and data flow diagram that illustrates interactions between entities and processes, the entity-relationship diagram was vital in the system's design and development. The ERD was used in the planning stage of system development because it helped identify system elements and their relationships, among other elements. That is, the ERD illustrates how entities relate to one another. The degree of mapping cardinalities was also shown in the ERD as one-to-one, one-to-many, many-to-one, or many-to-many type of relationship was established.

The developed system's entity-relationship diagram was shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Entity-Relationship Diagram

Data Dictionary

To further understand the description and definition of each data included in the developed system database, the proponents developed a data dictionary to provide additional details as to how each data was used. Data dictionary served as a reference, which includes the name of the data, its data type, size, and additional descriptions. Data dictionaries helped maintain the continuity and sustainability of systems or software projects because data dictionaries help future system developers understand the use of each data in the system.

Table 1 shows the sample data dictionary of the developed system.

Table 1: Sample Data Dictionary

tbl_resident			
Field Name	Data Type	Data Length	Description
brgy_id	varchar	99	The unique identification number of the barangay
resident_id	integer	10	The unique identification number of the resident
firstname	varchar	20	The first name of the resident composed of valid characters for first name
middlename	varchar	20	The middle name of the resident composed of valid characters for middle name
lastname	varchar	20	The last name of the resident composed of valid characters for last name
nickname	varchar	20	The nick name of the resident composed of valid characters for nick name
nameextension	varchar	20	The name extension of the resident composed of valid characters for name extension

birthday	varchar	30	The date of birth of the resident composed of letters and numbers following a birthday format.
age	integer	5	The age of the resident composed of numeric characters. Value must not be less than 0, no decimal points, and must only be whole number.
placeofbirth	varchar	50	The place of birth of the resident composed of valid alphanumeric characters.
sex	varchar	10	The biological sex assignment of the resident by birth
civilstatus	varchar	30	The civil status of the resident e.g. Single, Married, Widow, Separated
citizenship	varchar	50	The legal citizenship of the resident
occupation	varchar	50	The occupation of the resident
contactnumber	varchar	20	The contact number of the resident
brgygroup	varchar	50	The assigned barangay group of the resident
image	varchar	20	The unique code of the image to be stored in the database
status	varchar	30	The assigned status given to the resident record as to active or inactive status in the barangay

The following figures present the user interface of the developed system.

Figure 10: User Interface for the Log-In Form

Figure 11: System Main Dashboard

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Based on the proponents' processes starting from the planning to the analysis, design, and testing stages, the web-based Barangay Information and Records Management System was developed.

Figure 12: Resident Information Form

Name	Nick Name	Sex	Age	Civil Status	Contact Number	Barangay Section	Status	Address	Action	Update
Allison Tulamey Deles Santos	allie	Male	22	Married	0902842228	None	Active	403 Small St. St.	View	Update
Alvin Jose Andres	Alvin	Male	34	Married	0900000000	None	Active	404 Lomasan St.	View	Update
Bernice Mari Andrea Deles Santos	Bernice	Female	32	Single	0924752400	None	Active	402 Small St. St.	View	Update
Charli Dawn Dagat	charli	Female	42	Single	0900000000	None	Active	4022 Road St.	View	Update
Claraen Kyle Andros Deles Santos	Clara	Male	33	Single	0997217341	None	Active	405 Small St. St.	View	Update
Elaine Erentrich Andros	Elaine	Female	40	Single	0947901451	None	Active	405 Small St. St.	View	Update
Earl Crystal Andros Deles Santos	Earl	Male	15	Single	0917211571	None	Active	405 Small St. St.	View	Update
Francisco Manuel Guzman	Francis	Male	72	Single	0900000000	None	Active	4057 Road St.	View	Update
John Espinoza Capinpin	John	Male	44	Single	0900000000	None	Active	40 National St.	View	Update
Jay Zapena Castro	Jay	Male	22	Single	09979811282	None	Active	402 Lomasan St.	View	Update

Figure 13: List of Residents Form

The design and development of the Web-based Barangay Information and Records Management System commenced in the planning stage of the development life cycle. In the planning stage, the proponents gathered the requirements using different techniques such as observation in the barangay hall regarding the procedures and processes that took place every day, interviews with the key officials of the barangay and the barangay secretary, and documentary analysis on the available files and records to grasp vital information which is necessary for the design and development of the system. A review of the related literature and systems was also conducted to support the acquired information and validate the planning stage results.

Based on the planning stage's output, the necessary models and diagrams were developed to have a clearer understanding of how to develop the system. The presented user interfaces of the designed and developed web-based Barangay Information and Record Management System was developed based on models and diagrams presented in the methodology section. This study's proponents made the gathered requirements to transform the manual processes of recording, accessing, retrieving, and storing files and records in the barangay to an electronic and automated system.

Following the stages of carefully planning, analyzing, designing, coding, and testing, the proponents successfully came up with this IT solution to solve the manual system's problems. The system was developed using hypertext pre-processor, hypertext mark-up language, cascading style sheets, and MySQL. Integrating progressive UI framework, the proponents were able to develop an adaptive UI based on the type of devices used.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the processes conducted to design and develop the Web-Based Barangay Information and Records Management System, the following conclusions have been drawn:

1. The design and development of an IT system must religiously follow the stages of the development life cycle such as planning, analysis, design, development, and testing to come up with a more effective and efficient IT solution;
2. Data gathering techniques such as interview, observations, documentary analysis, and article reviews contribute to establishing a stronger foundation for developing IT solution;
3. Software design tools such as Data Flow Diagram, Use-Case Diagram, Entity Relationship Diagram, Database Normalization, and Data Dictionary are vital resources that must always be included in software development projects to better and clearer understand requirements and processes;
4. Hypertext Pre-processor and Structured Query Language is a useful tool in developing IT systems.
5. The designed and developed Barangay Information and Records Management System have transformed the manual process of recording, accessing, updating, removing, storing, and transmitting files and records effectively.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The proponents of this study recommend the following activities for future work.

1. Future researchers may utilize the results of this study to guide them in developing similar projects;
2. Further studies may be developed to assess the actual use and implementation of the system.
3. Continuous refinement of the system may be done to provide a more flexible and reliable system;
4. To effectively contribute to the body of knowledge, research models may also guide future researchers in understanding technology acceptance in the community.
5. Technology needs assessments may be done before the actual software development life cycle and an impact assessment after the implementation stage.

References

- Merriam-Webster. (n.d.).** Barangay. In *Merriam-Webster.com dictionary*. Retrieved November 2, 2020, from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/barangay>
- Pulumbarit JP. and Suarez JKG. (2017)** Barangay Office Management System. *International Journal of Mathematics & Computing*. 2017 Mar 31 [last modified: 2017 Jun 7]. Edition 1.
- Aparici, MM. and Ruelan, JR. (2018).** Web-Based Barangay Information System For Malita, Davao Occidental". Undergraduate Capstone Project
- Imus, JR., Magleo, ED., Soriano, MA., and Olalia, RL. (2018).** Barangay Management Information System (BMIS) for Cities and Municipalities in the Philippines. *International Journal of Computer Application*. ISSN 0975-8887. Volume 180 No. 19. February 2018.
- Javellana, J., Cainong, J., and Galvez, D. (2015).** An Integrated Information Management System for

Barangay 1-A Davao: Profiling, Incident Reporting, Project/Program Monitoring, and Document Request. 10.13140/RG.2.2.12966.52807

Lado, MJ., Maloloy-on, MI., Perez, GC., Rizaldo, PK., and Tacocong, SA. (2017). Computerized Information System in Barangay Poblacion, Danao City, Cebu. Retrieved from <https://www.slideshare.net/MarkJohnPerezLado/computerized-information-system-in-barangay-poblacion-danao-city-cebu>

Microsoft (2019). Description of Normalization. Retrieved from <https://docs.microsoft.com/en-us/office/troubleshoot/access/database-normalization-description#:~:text=Normalization%20is%20the%20process%20of,eliminating%20redundancy%20and%20inconsistent%20dependency.>